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DIFFERENTIAL *IN VITRO* FLOWERING RESPONSE OF MULBERRY SHOOT TIPS AS INFLUENCED BY MATURITY OF EXPLANTS AND MEDIA COMPOSITION

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In vitro flowering on mature apical shoot explants was observed in a study to standardize the micro propagation strategies for mulberry (*Morus alba*) cv. M-5 (Mysore-5). Only mature explants has shown this phenomenon and the best results was observed on MS medium supplemented with 2 mg Γ^1 BAP and 1 mg Γ^1 IAA. Probable reasons of this morphogenetic response and its applications in crop improvement are discussed along with similar records.

Key words : *In vitro* flowering, *Morus*, mulberry, tissue culture.

Abbreviations: BA- 6-Benzyl Amino Purine ; IAA- Indole 3-Acetic Acid ; MS- Murashige and Skoog.

INTRODUCTION

Mulberry (*Morus alba*) is a medium sized woody perennial tree grown throughout the tropical and sub tropical regions of the world. This plant assumes the primary importance as feed for the silk worm (*Bombyx mori*). The sweet fruits are also much relished. In mulberry, the multiplication procedure so far followed is only semi-hardwood cuttings. In any crop, the aim of mass multiplication will be fulfilled only when a high frequency regeneration protocol is standardized. Few attempts for direct regeneration from leaf (Oka and Ohyama, 1981 ; Vijayan *et al.*, 2000 ; Machii, 1990 ; Saito and Katagiri, 1989 ; Hossain *et al.*, 1992 ; Ivanica, 1987 ; Jain and Datta, 1992), cotyledon (Wang *et al.*, 1996) and anther (Shoukang *et al.*, 1987) explants were carried out and indirect regeneration (Srinivasa *et al.*, 2001 ; Narayanan *et al.*, 1989) was also reported. Even though few experiments were laid out using shoot explants (Kim *et al.*, 1985 ; Chung, 1985 ; Ghugale *et al.*, 1971), the frequency of regeneration was low and the maturity level of explants to be cultured were not specified. A study was carried out to standardize the micro propagation strategies in mulberry. In the study, a unique phenomenon of *in vitro* flowering from shoot tips was observed

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Explants of freshly germinated shoots tip from axillary bud and mature shoot tips of apical origin were used in the study. Apical shoots shown a higher maturity compared to fresh axillary shoots used. *In situ* grown shoot tips were collected and sterilized using 0.1 per cent mercuric chloride followed by 70 per cent ethanol dip for 15 seconds. The explants were washed thoroughly for 5-6 times with sterile double distilled water and were cultured aseptically on MS medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) supplemented with 3 per cent sucrose and different concentrations and combinations of growth regulators. The following growth regulator combinations were tried in the study:

IN VITRO FLOWERING RESPONSE OF MULBERRY SHOOTS

1. 0.5 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ IAA
2. 0.5 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 1.0 mg l⁻¹ IAA
3. 1.0 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ IAA
4. 1.0 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ IAA
5. 2.0 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ IAA
6. 2.0 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 1.0 mg l⁻¹ IAA
7. 1.0 mg l⁻¹ Kinetin + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ IAA
8. 2.0 mg l⁻¹ Kinetin + 1.0 mg l⁻¹ IAA
9. 3.0 mg l⁻¹ Kinetin + 1.0 mg l⁻¹ IAA
10. 4.0 mg l⁻¹ Kinetin + 1.0 mg l⁻¹ IAA
11. 0.25 mg l⁻¹ zeatin + 0.25 mg l⁻¹ IAA
12. 0.5 mg l⁻¹ zeatin + 0.25 mg l⁻¹ IAA
13. 1.0 mg l⁻¹ zeatin + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ IAA
14. 2.0 mg l⁻¹ zeatin + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ IAA
15. 0.5 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 0.25 mg l⁻¹ GA₃
16. 1.0 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ GA₃
17. 2.0 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ GA₃
18. 4.0 mg l⁻¹ BAP + 0.5 mg l⁻¹ GA₃

Cultures were incubated at 25° C and 16 hours of photoperiod. Every 5 days, explants were transferred to fresh media and observations on flowering i.e., number of shoots showing flowering, average number of flowers per shoot, type of shoots showing flowering in each treatment were recorded from 21st day of initial culture. Other tissue cultural operations were followed as per the procedure outlined by Vijayan *et al.* (2000). In this discussion emphasis is given only for *in vitro* flowering and treatments showing such a response are detailed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Root Morphogenesis on Specified Media:

The morphogenic responses on shoot tip explants of mulberry as influenced by BAP and IAA combinations are presented in Table I. In this study only a combination of BAP and IAA growth regulators has given *in vitro* flowering. Root induction was observed from the cut ends of shoot tips at various levels. Immature axillary shoots shown a better rooting response. Few long roots were induced at the basal end of immature shoots when 0.5 mg l⁻¹ IAA was used, but no rooting was observed on mature shoots. A higher concentration of 1 mg l⁻¹ IAA has induced profuse hairy root like structures on immature shoots and few long roots on mature shoots.

Table I. *In vitro* flowering and root induction responses on shoot tip explants of mulberry (treatments showing *in vitro* flowering response are presented).

Tableau I. Floraison in vitro et réponses d'induction de racines avec des explants d'extrémités de pousses de mûrier (les traitements montrant une réponse de floraison in vitro sont présentés).

Treatments	MS medium with growth regulators (mg.l ⁻¹)	Number of explants cultured	Number of explants showing flowering	Average number of flowers induced	Number of shoots in vegetative stage	Rooting response
Traitements	Milieu MS avec des régulateurs de croissance (mg.l ⁻¹)	Nombre d'explants cultivés	Nombre d'explants présentant une floraison induites	Nombre moyen de fleurs induites	Nombre de pousses au stade végétatif	Réponse de racinement
I. Mature shoots of axillary origin / I. Pousses matures d'origine axillaire						
T1	0.5 BAP + 0.5 IAA	25	-	-	25	3-6 long roots 3-6 racines longues
T2	0.5 BAP + 1.0 IAA	25	-	-	25	Sparse short roots Racines courtes éparses
T3	1.0 BAP + 0.5 IAA	25	-	-	25	5-10 long roots 5-10 racines longues
T4	1.0 BAP + 1.0 IAA	25	-	-	25	Profuse hairy root growth Croissance de racines abondantes et touffues
T5	2.0 BAP + 0.5 IAA	25	-	-	25	5-8 long roots 5-8 racines longues
T6	2.0 BAP + 1.0 IAA	25	-	-	25	Profuse rooting Racinement abondant
II. Mature shoots of apical origin / II. Pousses matures d'origine apicale						
T7	0.5 BAP + 0.5 IAA	25	-	-	25	No rooting Pas de racinement
T8	0.5 BAP + 1.0 IAA	25	-	-	25	2-3 long roots 2-3 racines longues
T9	1.0 BAP + 0.5 IAA	25	8	1.875	17	No rooting Pas de racinement
T10	1.0 BAP + 1.0 IAA	25	6	2.333	19	4-7 long roots 4-7 pousses longues
T11	2.0 BAP + 0.5 IAA	25	18	2.666	7	3-4 long roots 3-4 pousses longues
T12	2.0 BAP + 1.0 IAA	25	22	3.500	3	8-12 long roots 8-12 racines longues

Fig. 1. *In vitro* flowering on mature mulberry shoot tip explant on MS medium supplemented with $1.0 \text{ mg } \Gamma^{-1}$ BAP and $0.5 \text{ mg } \Gamma^{-1}$ IAA, after 21 days of inoculation.

Fig. 1. Floraison *in vitro* avec un explant d'extrémité de pousse de mûrier mature sur du milieu MS additionné avec $1,0 \text{ mg } \Gamma^{-1}$ de BAP et $0,5 \text{ mg } \Gamma^{-1}$ d'IAA 21 jours après l'inoculation.

2. Effect of explant maturity on *in vitro* flowering:

In vitro flowering was observed on mature apical current season shoot tips of eight months from six years and four months old plants inoculated on medium with BAP and IAA. The immature shoots from axillary buds failed to produce any flowering. In previous studies (Mhatre *et al.*, 1985 ; Tewary and Subba Rao, 1990) also, axillary immature shoots cultured failed to produce *in vitro* flowering. The flowers might have developed from performed flower buds already present in the tissue. On immature shoots, the apical dominance maintains a high level vegetative status. When shoot attains

maturity, a shift from vegetative to reproductive stage happens leading to induction of flower buds. This may be the reason for the presence of rudimentary flower buds on mature shoot tips. Similar result of *in vitro* flower induction on internodal explants of jasmine collected from mature orthotropic shoots is reported (Dhanraj, 1999). Jammal *et al.* (1991) also made similar observations in spinach cultures and opined that the stimulus for flowering might be produced in the shoot region without the involvement of roots. In this study also, flowering was observed on mature explants inoculated on MS medium with different levels of BAP and 0.5 mg l^{-1} IAA with no root induction; substantiating the statement that root activity is not the reason for flower induction (Plate 1). Both male and female flowers were observed and its ratio was not influenced by growth regulators and no sex reversal was observed.

In the field, the flower buds are produced on mature stems in mulberry and flowering is influenced by the availability of nutrients. Under *in vitro* conditions, availability of nutrients will not be a problem, which leads to ready out-burst of flower buds. After a certain level of growth, the nutrients absorbed along the cut end of shoot bud will not be sufficient to maintain the vegetative and reproductive growth simultaneously. These conditions might have led to the drying up of the induced flower on shoots with no roots (Plate 1). In such cultures early yellowing of leaves was observed perhaps due to lesser availability of nutrients or by the enhanced ethylene production by withering flowers.

3. Effect of growth regulators on *in vitro* flowering:

Medium with a higher level of cytokinin has induced higher number of flowers per explants (plate 2). This is in accordance with the results of previous *in vitro* flowering reports (Scorza and Janick, 1978 and 1980 and Scorza, 1979) which argued that cytokinin is a must for *in vitro* flowering. A high-level cytokinin can induce flower from a bud, which remains dormant at lower concentration (Scorza, 1979). The use of IAA in combination with BAP in inducing shoot proliferation is already discussed. The efficiency of IAA and Kinetin interaction on bringing out *in vitro* flowering is reported (Tepfer *et al.*, 1966). IAA shifts the protein synthesis and favour morphological developments in the plant system (Wardell and Skoog, 1969). This may be the reason for development of other wise dormant flower bud. *In vitro* flowering is also reported to be the result of a combination of hormones (Van, 1980).

4. Similar reports and applications in crop improvement:

The unique phenomenon of *in vitro* flowering is already reported in other tree species such as citrus (Tisserat *et al.*, 1990) and Japanese pear (Higashiuchi *et al.*, 1990, Tsujikawa *et al.*, 1990). In potato, flowering from the callus cultures is reported (Hassan *et al.*, 1989; Al-Warch *et al.*, 1989). In seed producing species such as Nicotiana (Dien and Van, 1974), passion fruit (Scorza and Janick, 1978 and 1980, Scorza, 1979), streptocarpus (Handro, 1983; Siromonds, 1987) and Syringa (Skrzypezak, 1992), this phenomenon can be efficiently used in crop husbandry by ensuring the purity of pollen by *in vitro* pollination strategies; opening a wide avenue of crop breeding. Breeding process in Amaranthus (Brent and Paul, 1998) in which *in vitro* self pollination and seed germination is reported, spinach (Jammal *et al.*, 1991), cucumber (Msikita *et al.*, 1990), cichory (Bais *et al.*, 2000), *Brassica napus* (Koh and Loh, 2000) and garden pea (Franklin *et al.*, 2000) could be accelerated due to the assured purity in crosses. In essential oil producing plants such as rose (Susmita and Debata, 1996) and jasmine (Dhanraj, 1999), oils with high level purity can be obtained within a short span. In flowering ornamentals such as Kalanchoe (Dickens *et al.*, 1990) and Dimorpotheca (Al-Atabee and Power, 1990), non flowering ornamentals such as Panax (Tang, 2000) and Chenopodium (Mitrovic *et al.*, 2000) and field crops such as Pearl Millet (Devi *et al.*, 1990), this assumes lot of applications in breeding. Bamboo is unique for its monocarpic flowering. *In vitro* flowering reduces the time-required for flowering from many years to 2 months (Gielis and Raichaudhuri, 1999). Right

Fig 2. *In vitro* flowering on mature mulberry shoot tip on MS medium supplemented with $2.0 \text{ mg } \Gamma^{-1}$ IAA, 21 days after inoculation.

Fig 2. Floraison *in vitro* de l'extrémité de pousse de mûrier mature sur du milieu MS additionné avec $2 \text{ mg } \Gamma^{-1}$ de BAP et $1,0 \text{ mg } \Gamma^{-1}$ IAA, 21 jours après l'inoculation.

from the first reported tissue culture experiment in mulberry (Ohyama, 1970), no *in vitro* flowering is reported so far.

In mulberry the flowers will not set seeds but produce fruits parthenocarpically. *In vitro* flowering can be used to harvest high quality fruits, to study the mechanism of flowering and the response of phytochrome to flowering (Handro, 1983, Simmonds, 1987).

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